

Atmosphères — György Ligeti

Jason Noble, 2018

For the original, full version of this publication, visit:

<https://timbreandorchestration.org/writings/amazing-moments-in-timbre/2018/11/23/atmospheres>

We're beginning our "amazing moments in timbre" series with a true classic, György Ligeti's paralyzingly beautiful orchestral masterpiece *Atmosphères* (1961). This is one of the relatively few avant-garde compositions from the second half of the 20th century to gain popular recognition, due in part to its inclusion in the soundtrack to Stanley Kubrick's film *2001: A Space Odyssey*. It takes Schoenberg's idea of *Klangfarbenmelodie*, in which sound-colour or timbre assumes the focal role traditionally held by melody, to a whole new level. The opening chord has become one of the go-to examples of *sound mass*, complex combinations of many sounds that tend to fuse together into a perceptual totality. Listen to a recording, with a graphical diagram of the music's organization in pitch space, here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JWlwCRIVh7M>